

Funding and obstacles for building capacities

The CESSDA ERIC case

Irena Vipavc Brvar | ADP and Chair CESSDA Training Working Group

CESSDA Widening meeting, Skopje, 5-6 November 2019

Human resources (CESSDA SAW D3.3)

- ◆ What **kinds of skills and capacities** are necessary at first or can be developed later on?
- ◆ **How many** staff members are needed in order to successfully carry out the objectives?
- ◆ How many staff members **are really possible** given available resources, and what are the implications of this with respect to the services and goals? In terms of human resources, what is the bare minimum needed to operate a national data service in the country?
- ◆ What kind of **internal structure** will be there in place?
- ◆ What will be the **roles and responsibilities** of different staff members?

Data service manager (CESSDA SAW D3.3)

Profile: Management skills; strong communication skills; social sciences background; proponent of open data and research transparency

Main activities:

- ◆ Management of the data service
- ◆ Setting of policy and procedural rules
- ◆ Relations with national and international stakeholders and partners
- ◆ Data service promotion towards the research community (the beneficiaries)

Data specialist (CESSDA SAW D3.3)

Profile: Systems administration, software programming and database management, software development and maintenance, overall understanding of data exchange protocols in a networked environment and security issues associated with it

Main activities:

- ◆ Install and maintain servers
- ◆ Install and maintain hardware for staff
- ◆ Install and maintain software to archiving and dissemination of data
- ◆ Develop and maintain data service website

It specialist (CESSDA SAW D3.3)

Profile: Management skills; strong communication skills; social sciences background; proponent of open data and research transparency

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Mission of the archive

- ◊ Sharing your data with us ensures that your data will be **professionally curated and managed**.
- ◊ All data disseminated have undergone **rigorous checks** to ensure that they have been **fully anonymised**, thus protecting the individual data confidentiality.
- ◊ **Data are enhanced through the creation of metadata** based on the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) international standard for describing statistical and social science data.
- ◊ We are committed to **maintaining data** resources for **the long term**, ensuring that, as data formats evolve and advance, the archive's holdings are always available in easily accessible forms.
- ◊ *We hold Data Seal of Approval (DSA), a certification for trusted data repositories.

What will you offer?

What will you offer?

Will you do everything on your own ([example ISSDA](#))

Can you share personnel with other departments?

Are there any institutional regulations or national law that apply? GDPR!

To which communities?

[Services for Researchers](#)

[Services for Students](#)

[Services for Teachers](#)

[Services for Research Funders](#)

Data formats ?

- ◆ Tabular data with extensive metadata
- ◆ Tabular data with minimal metadata
- ◆ Geospatial data (vector and raster data)
- ◆ Textual data
- ◆ Image data
- ◆ Video data
- ◆ Documentation and scripts

FSD'S main functions

FSD'S MAIN FUNCTIONS ARE

- ③ data acquisition
- ③ processing and preserving archived data
- ③ providing metadata for archived data
- ③ supervising use conditions set for data
- ③ delivering data to users
- ③ providing other information services related to data
- ③ promoting data reuse
- ③ promoting good practices in data collection and reuse
- ③ supporting research methods teaching
- ③ providing information on data archiving activities
- ③ participating in international data archive collaboration

IN ADDITION TO ITS MAIN FUNCTIONS FSD

- ③ participates in developing data processing practices at national and international level
- ③ organises and promotes social science research and teaching
- ③ produces publications on relevant issues
- ③ develops other relevant services

Source: <https://www.fsd.uta.fi/en/data-archive/#operating-principles>

Policy of digital preservation

Compliance with the OAIS and Core Trustworthy Data Repositories Requirements v01.00.

Source: Digital preservation policy (2017), ADP

Tools and standards

CESSDA Technical Infrastructure Training Day

5. December 2019
Tampere / Finland

The CESSDA Technical Infrastructure Training Day will be held on 5th December 2019.

Follow-up to the [EDDI18](#) CESSDA technical training event.
It will cover:

- ◊ deploying an application on the CESSDA Technical infrastructure (from commit, via build and test in development and staging to deployment in the production environment)
- ◊ using the CESSDA public APIs;
- ◊ distributed logging.

For CESSDA Service Provider staff working on the implementation of CESSDA Tools and Services and of their own back office systems.

Tools and standards

Diversity Scholarships

3. – 4. December 2019
Tampere / Finland

EUROPEAN DDI USER CONFERENCE

2. December 2019

TUTORIALS

What can DDI do for you? An introduction to the DDI	Let's take a look at the DDI-documented paradata collected by the information system of a longitudinal panel!
Beyond documenting a codebook...using DDI to support the management and processing of metadata	Generating DDI 4 in the Language of your Choice

Tools

European Dataverse Workshop 2020

Representatives from (European) research institutions that are using, or planning to use, [Dataverse](#) to run their research data repositories, and, more generally, research institutions that are looking for a repository software.

January 23-24, 2020 (during the Northern Lights season!)

held at UiT The Arctic University of Norway

Open source research data repository software

Tools / statistical packages / RDM

The Coursera logo, featuring the word "coursera" in a blue, lowercase, sans-serif font.

Coursework **Many free**

Each course is like an interactive textbook, featuring pre-recorded videos, quizzes, and projects.

Certificates

Earn official recognition for your work, and share your success with friends, colleagues, and employers.

www.cessda.eu

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

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[TOOLS & SERVICES](#) [TRAINING](#) [DATA CATALOGUE](#)

Data Catalogue

The CESSDA Data Catalogue contains the metadata of all data in the holdings of CESSDA's service providers. It is a one-stop-shop for search and discovery, enabling effective access to European social science research data.

Data Management Expert Guide

This guide is designed by European experts to help social science researchers make their research data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.

Training

The CESSDA Training website provides a collection of resources and events for learning about the management, preservation and distribution of research data.

CESSDA Training

It is part of CESSDA's mission to facilitate teaching and learning in the social sciences. CESSDA has a [Training Working Group](#) that is responsible for supporting continuous learning and training of its Service Provider staff and the social science user community. The Training Group maintains the information on this training website.

We focus on training for

- data producers,
- data users,
- data professionals and CESSDA Service Provider staff.

You can find training, advice and educational resources on:

- [discovering and using data](#),
- [managing research data](#),
- [preserving data and using CESSDA's tools and services](#).

Featured Resource

Data Management Expert Guide

Put social scientists like yourself at the heart of making their research data findable, understandable, sustainably accessible and reusable

cessda
DMEG Data Management
Expert Guide

CESSDA Training Working Group (2017-2018). *CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide*. Bergen, Norway: CESSDA ERIC.

Retrieved from

<https://www.cessda.eu/DMEG>

Recurring elements - DMP

CESSDA
Consortium of European
Social Sciences Data Archives

Adapt your Data Management Plan

A list of Data Management Questions based on the
Expert Tour Guide on Data Management

This CESSDA list of Data Management Questions (2017) is licensed under a
Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License.

The CESSDA Expert Tour Guide on Data Management is available at <https://www.cessda.eu/DMGuide>

PLAN

Overview

Title of the project

Date of this plan

Description of the project

- What is the nature of the project?
- What is the research question?
- What is the project time line?

Origin of Data

- What kind of data will be used during the project?
- If you are reusing existing data: What is the scope, volume and format? How are different data sources integrated?
- If you are collecting new data can you clarify why this is necessary?

Principal researchers

- Who are the main researchers involved?
- What are their contact details?

Collaborating researchers (if applicable)

- What are their contact details and their roles in the project?

Funder (if applicable)

- If funding is granted, what is the reference number of the funding granted?

Data producer

- Which organisation has the administrative responsibility for the data?

Project data contact

- Who can be contacted about the project after it has finished?

Data owner(s)

- Which organisation(s) own(s) the data?
- If several organisations are involved, which organisation owns what data?

Roles

- Who is responsible for updating the DMP and making sure that it's followed?
- Do project participants have any specific roles?
- What is the project time line?

Costs

- Are there costs you need to consider to buy specific software or hardware?
- Are there costs you need to consider for storage and backup?
- Are potential expenses for (preparing the data for) archiving covered?

Adapt your DMP: Part 1

« Previous Next »

Search this guide Search

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is an important tool to structure the research data management of your project. After working on each chapter you should be able to answer part of the questions which make up a DMP.

This is the first of six 'Adapt your DMP' sections in this tour guide. When you have finished the chapter on data management planning, you can start filling in the 'Overview of your research project' section. Below you can see what elements and corresponding questions are generally included in that section. You can select appropriate questions and answer them to adapt your own DMP.

For easy reference, we have put together a list of DMP-questions for all chapters in this tour guide. You can [view and download it](#) (CESSDA, 2017) and keep it as a reference while you are studying the contents of this guide.

- + Title of the project
- + Date and version of this plan
- + Description of the project
- + Origin of the data
- + Principal and collaborating researchers
- + Funder (if applicable)
- + Data producer
- + Project data contact
- + Data owner(s)
- + Roles
- + Costs

Updating country specific parts

- ◇ [Data management requirements in your country](#)
- ◇ [Ethical reviews and committees](#)
- ◇ [Data protection and consent form](#)
- ◇ [Copyright law](#)

If you want your national information to be added please contact us by Nov. 15

RDM and other CESSDA trainings

www.cessda.eu/DMEG/TTT

- ◆ Train the trainers (2018 Ljubljana, 2019 Athens)
- ◆ Local events (budget for and expert):
 - ◆ Workshops in 2018, in Lithuania, in Denmark and Netherlands where the DMEG was presented.
 - ◆ in 2019: Croatia, Germany, Bosna and Hercegovina
- ◆ Topical webinars

 YouTube

CESSDA expert seminar

2019	Colchester, UK	CESSDA tools and services
2018	Ljubljana, Si	CESSDA technical infrastructure
2017	Bergen, NO	Revised legal and ethical framework for archiving and re-use/use of new types of data
2016	Prague, CZ	Developing components for the Research Infrastructure
2015	The Hague, NL	Trust Project
2014	Colchester, UK	Research integrity - a digital curation problem?
2013	Vienna, AT	Research Data Management: Cost and Incentives
2012	Tampere, FI	Data Acquisition and Licence Agreements
2011	Lausanne, CH	Question data banks - towards greater integration

**FIRST in 1987 in Odense, Denmark:
From Localisation to Cataloguing of Data Sets**

Resource directory to be moved

Home My Library Groups People Documentation Forums Get Involved

Home > Groups > [CESSDA Resource Directory](#) > Library > [CESSDA Archive Resource Directory \(CARD\)](#)

Library

- CESSDA Archive Resource Directory (CARD)
 - 0. General
 - 1. Definition of the organisation
 - 2. Services and activities
 - 3. Staffing, management and financing
 - 4. Technical infrastructure
 - 5. Communication and promotion
 - 6. Partner support and promotion
 - 7. Evaluation and certification
- Trash

Tags

Development ... Development ... Development ...

Resource for... Resource for... Resource for... Resource for...

Resource for... Resource for... Resource for... Resource typ...

Resource typ... Resource typ...

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Title	Creator	Item Type	Year	Added By
Access Policies and Usage Regulations: Licenses	CESSDA SaW	Video Recording	2016	FORS.cb
Acquisition Policy - FORS	FORS	Report	2017	FORS.cb
Analyses of Frameworks (DASISH D4.1 Appendix 5)	DASISH	Report	2014	FORS.cb
Analysis of existing potential for the establishment of a so...	SERSCIDA	Report	2013	FORS.cb
Analysis of existing potential for the establishment of a so...	SERSCIDA	Report	2013	FORS.cb
Analysis of existing potential for the establishment of a so...	SERSCIDA	Report	2013	FORS.cb
Anonymization checks for open-access data	AUSSDA	Report		FORS.cb
Archive Training Manual	UKDS	Web Page	2018	FORS.cb
Archive Training Manual	SERSCIDA	Report	2013	FORS.cb
Best Practice Guide for the Registration of Resources with d...	GESIS	Report	2014	FORS.cb
Business process modelling and systems architecture expertis...	DANS	Interview		FORS.cb
Capability Maturity Modelling Expertise	DANS	Interview		FORS.cb
CESSDA Archive Development Canvas	CESSDA SaW	Report	2017	FORS.cb
CESSDA Capability Development Model	CESSDA SaW	Web Page	2016	FORS.cb
CESSDA Cost-Benefit Advocacy Toolkit	CESSDA SaW	Interview	2017	FORS.cb

CESSDA Training days

27. - 28. November 2019, Cologne

Tools and Services for Service Provider (or other repository) staff

- ◊ Introduction to Digital Preservation – for new service provider staff
- ◊ Preparing Metadata for the CESSDA Data Catalogue
- ◊ CESSDA Vocabulary Service
- ◊ Documentation and Metadata for Geodata
- ◊ Documentation and Metadata for Social Media Data

Tools and Services for Researchers

- ◊ Harmonization of variables, including case studies with real data
- ◊ Geodata Referencing with ESS Case Study
- ◊ Data Linking – Surveys, Social Media, and Geo data

Events relevant for data archivists

DATA BY DESIGN

IASSIST 2020 · Gothenburg

May 19 - May 22, 2020

[Deadline for presentation and Workshop submission](#)

6.12.2019

[IASSIST Fellows Program](#)

Application deadline 17.1.2020

Deadline for **early fee**

15.3.2020

IASSIST 2019

[Data Down Under: Exploring “Data Firsts”](#)

Sydney, Australia, May 27-31, 2019

[» Presentations](#)

IASSIST

iBlog

IASSIST Quarterly

Event sponsorship (2017, 2019)

**REGIONAL ROUND TABLE:
LEGAL AND ETHICAL ISSUES IN RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT
AND OPEN SCIENCE IN SEE COUNTRIES**

THE RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

www.rd-alliance.org

*building the social and technical bridges
that enable open sharing of data*

**32 FLAGSHIP
OUTPUTS**

of which 4 ICT
Technical
Specifications

**75 ADOPTION
CASES**

across multiple
disciplines,
organisations &
countries

**104 GROUPS WORKING ON
GLOBAL DATA
INTEROPERABILITY CHALLENGES**

*of which 35 WORKING GROUPS
& 67 INTEREST GROUPS*

**8,642 INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS
FROM 137 COUNTRIES**

67,9% Academia & Research
14,2% Public Administration
12,7% Enterprise & Industry

**50 ORGANISATIONAL MEMBERS &
8 AFFILIATE MEMBERS**

Vision

Researchers and innovators openly share data across technologies, disciplines, and countries to address the grand challenges of society.

Mission

RDA builds the **social and technical bridges** that **enable open sharing** of data.

[SURCE: RDA web page](http://www.rd-alliance.org)

WWW.RD-ALLIANCE.ORG

@RESDATALL

CC BY-SA

GUIDING PRINCIPLES

- ◎ **OPENNESS**
Membership is open to all interested individuals who subscribe to the RDA's Guiding Principles. RDA community meetings and processes are open, and the deliverables of RDA working Groups will be publicly disseminated.
- ◎ **CONSENSUS**
The RDA moves forward by achieving consensus among its membership. RDA processes and procedures include appropriate mechanisms to resolve conflicts.
- ◎ **BALANCE**
The RDA seeks to promote balanced representation of its membership and stakeholder communities.
- ◎ **HARMONIZATION**
The RDA works to achieve harmonization across data standards, policies, technologies, infrastructure and communities.
- ◎ **COMMUNITY - DRIVEN**
The RDA is a public, community-driven body constituted of volunteer members and organizations, supported by the RDA Secretariat.
- ◎ **NON-PROFIT**
RDA does not promote, endorse, or sell commercial products, technologies or services.

RDA Supporting Outputs

Data Discovery Paradigms: User Requirements and Recommendations for Data Repositories

The Challenge: When there are multiple data repositories, researchers presents a wide range of choices.

What is the solution? By gathering a set of functional requirements and proposed implementation for data repositories.

Income Streams for Data Repositories

The Challenge: Basic functions to increase alternative income streams.

What is the solution? The RDA Data Center recovery possible body of twenty.

23 Things For Research Data Management

The Challenge: Build capacity within the library community around research data management, ensure libraries are aligned with other research data management service providers, and share practices as new library services evolve and mature.

What is the solution? 23 Things: Libraries for Research Data provides an overview of practical, free, online resources and tools that librarians can begin using today to incorporate research data management into the daily practice of librarianship. Available in 11 languages, the resource groups 23 free, online resources to help librarians address issues on data management such as Metadata, Digital Preservation, Data Repositories, Data Licensing and Privacy or Data Citation.

Produced by: **Libraries for Research Data Interest Group**
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/libraries-research-data.html>

Legal Interoperability of Research Data: Principles

The Challenge: Providing researchers with aspects entailed when they

What is the solution? The CODATA-RDA Legal Issues related to the outcome is a set of guidelines. They are offered to the research community: librarians, archivists, administrators, individuals are engaged in activities research data from diverse their greatest benefits.

Produce Interop
<https://www.ata-legi>

Research Data Repository Interoperability Principles

The Challenge: Huge amounts of data repository small audience.

What is the solution? On the one hand, underlying data and number of the other hand, repository platform potential. The interoperability consensus on repository inter

Matrix of use cases and functional requirements for research data repository platform

The Challenge: Gather and analyze research data use cases in the context of repository platform requirements.

What is the solution? Based on use cases, the matrix describes forty-four functional requirements identified for research data repository platforms and provides a score identifying relative importance. These functional requirement scores can be used to assess research data repository platforms and to prioritize functional requirements for development and adoption.

Produced by: **Repository Platforms for Research Data IG**
<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/repository-platforms-research-data.html>

SURCE: [RDA web page](#)

RDA: Who? What? Where?

Introducing the Research Data Alliance

and its Opportunities

for the Social Sciences

[SOURCE: 10.5281/zenodo.1401105](https://zenodo.org/record/1401105)

**Prepared by Ricarda Braukmann from
DANS / RDA Ambassador**

Social Science Research Data IG

Chair (s): Ron Dekker, Jonathan Crabtree, Steven McEachern

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/social-science-research-data-ig>

RDA Europe offered financial support to Early Career European Researchers & Scientists working with data to attend the [14th RDA Plenary meeting](#),

Statistical methods training

49th GESIS Spring Seminar: Digital Behavioral Data

Date: 02.03 - 20.03.2020 ics-file

Week 1

Week 1: Fundamentals of Data Analysis with Python

02.03.2020 - 06.03.2020 - **Dr. John McLevey, Jillian Anderson**

EUROLAB Grants

to work on data available at GESIS

Week 2

Week 2: A Practical Introduction to Machine Learning in Python

09.03.2020 - 13.03.2020 - **Dr. Damian Trilling, Dr. Anne Kroon**

GESIS Grants

Week 3

Week 3: Social Network Analysis with Digital Behavioral Data

16.03.2020 - 20.03.2020 - **Dr. David Garcia, Max Pellert**

GESIS Summer School in Survey
Methodology

Coming in next months

- ◊ Webinar - Digital divide based on the survey data collected in the World Internet Project (EKKE) **28.11.**
- ◊ EQB (GESIS) **29.11.**
- ◊ **QAMYDATA** (UKDS) **2.12.**
NCRM-funded UK Data Service project to develop a **light weight, open-source tool for quality assessment of research data**
A **'data health check'** tool that identifies the most common problems in data submitted in disciplines that utilise quantitative methods

Thank you for your attention!

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 cessda.eu

 [@CESSDA_Data](https://twitter.com/CESSDA_Data)

